

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HOUSING AFFORDABILITY AND FAMILY STABILITY IN LAGOS, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Unaffordable housing is one of the major causes of family instability in Lagos, Nigeria. In cities experiencing rapid industrial and economic growth, with the potential to attract many people, housing rents are skyrocketing, leading to chaos. This study analysed the relationship between family stability and affordable housing in Lagos, Nigeria, using a descriptive approach. A small sample of 50 households was collected across low, middle, and high-income neighbourhoods by administering questionnaires that focused on sociodemographic characteristics, housing costs, affordability indicators, and family stability measures. The findings from this study indicate an inverse relationship between affordable housing and family stability. A significant number of households spend more than 40% of their annual income on housing rent. Families that spend a higher percentage of their annual income on house rent tend to face frequent relocation, disruption of children's schooling, and reduced household functionality.

Keywords: Housing affordability; Income; Lagos- Nigeria; Family Instability

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Affordable housing has become a growing concern in most Nigerian cities, particularly in Lagos. Lagos, Nigeria's fastest-growing economic hub and tourist destination, has continued to experience rapid urbanization, population growth, and increasing housing demand (Oyewo, O.T and Oyewale, O.O, 2023). Consequently, housing costs in Lagos have risen significantly, with most rents outpacing household incomes. Access to affordable, decent housing is a basic need for families to grow and live comfortably in. Outrageous house rents and associated bills inhibit proper living conditions and are strong reasons for family instability, thereby depreciating family well-being and long-term development (Aluko, 2012). When families secure financially sustainable housing, they are more likely to experience consistency in employment, education, health, and interpersonal relationship outcomes.

Lagos, Nigeria, is projected to have a population of approximately 17.8 million by 2025, up from 21 million in 2016 (Macrotrends, 2026). The Nigerian population is estimated to be approximately 240 million (Worldometer, 2026); hence, Lagos comprises almost 8 percent of that population. As the population continues to increase, there is not enough accommodation; therefore, the first-come, first-served system is not viable. The growing population is driven by Lagos's industrial and economic strength (Auwalu, F. K., & Bello, M., 2023), with the possibility of improved employment, health care facilities, bursaries, business loans, and other social amenities. Aside from rapid population growth, another important factor that continues to hinder access to decent, affordable housing in Lagos is the role of house agents and real estate agencies in the rental and sales markets (Bamiteko, O. D., & Adebisi, O. O., 2020).

In many parts of the city, particularly within low- and middle-income neighbourhoods, housing agents act as intermediaries between landlords and tenants. They are meant to reduce the hassle of house hunting, but, on the contrary, their activities have increased the overall cost of housing beyond control. The commission usually requested by this agent amounts to about 30 to 40 percent of the annual rent, excluding other charges such as agreement, caution, and inspection fees. Similarly, some real estate agencies in Lagos contribute to rising housing costs by marketing and pricing properties at exorbitant rates, often targeting high-income earners and excluding low- and middle-income families. They usually justify these high prices by citing the location, perceived prestige associated with the location, or prospective future property value.

This study examines the effect of housing affordability on family stability in Lagos, Nigeria, drawing on real estate market analyses, relevant scholarly literature, and official government housing reports.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The Author Ola Aluko (2011) discussed the effects of location and neighbourhood on housing values in metropolitan Lagos. This study analyzed how spatial variations in location and neighbourhood characteristics influence housing prices across different zones in Lagos. The study used analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple regression models to test the hypothesis that housing prices vary significantly across neighbourhoods and locational attributes, such as major landmarks. The study concluded that neighbourhoods and locations play a more significant role in determining housing values when housing markets are analyzed at smaller geographical scales, thereby offering important insights into the structure and functioning of the urban housing market in Nigerian cities.

Olanipekun T. Alaba and O. J. Adegoke (2015) investigated the relationship between lending interest rates and housing prices in the Lagos Metropolis. This study primarily used questionnaires administered to registered Estate Surveying Firms in Lagos State and secondary data on lending interest rates spanning a 15-year period. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to analyze the data. The results show an increasing trend in housing prices, despite a gradual decline in lending interest rates over the study period. This shows a strong negative relationship between lending interest rates and house prices across housing categories in Lagos, Nigeria. The study concluded that interest rates significantly influence housing prices in Lagos, although location factors remain particularly important in shaping price variations across the metropolis.

O. A. Akinjare et al. (2011) discussed the effects of landfill sites on residential property values in Lagos, Nigeria. This study addresses the long-standing debate on the impact of solid waste disposal facilities on housing prices. A thorough analysis of four landfill sites with varying sizes, operational statuses and historical backgrounds was conducted. Values were assigned to properties based on a distance gradient within a 1.2 km radius of each landfill using concentric rings at 300-metre intervals. The findings revealed a clear inverse relationship between proximity to landfills and residential property values, with housing located closer to landfill sites experiencing significant depreciations. With an average of 5.75 percent across the study area, property appreciation increased with distance.

The authors, Olalekan Dimeji Bamiteko and Oyeyemi Omodadepe Adebisi (2020) analysed the effect of neighbourhood security on housing prices in Lagos State, Nigeria, with a focus on Amuwo-Odofin Local Government Area. This study discusses the role of rapid urban population growth, unemployment, and rising crime rates in shaping housing market outcomes. Using primary survey data collected from 140 residents and analyzed through Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, the findings demonstrate that neighbourhood security features, such as fenced apartments, the presence of gatemen, and local security or vigilante services, have a positive and significant influence on housing prices. The study found that high crime rates negatively affect housing values and concluded that residents are willing to pay higher prices to reside in secure, crime-free neighbourhoods, thereby highlighting the significance of security as a key determinant of housing prices in Lagos.

The author, Victor Ilechukwu (2024), examined the impact of COVID-19-related government interventions on residential housing prices in Lagos, Nigeria. This study addresses a gap in the existing literature by focusing on the housing market rather than financial markets. Using a difference-in-difference approach supported by descriptive statistics, this study compared housing price trends before the pandemic (2009 and 2015) with market outcomes during the pandemic using the 2020 Lagos Property Market Consensus Report. The findings indicate that several factors related to government intervention significantly affect house prices: places with stricter lockdown measures and rising infection rates are associated with higher housing fees.

Based on the role of intermediaries, Bamiteko and Adebisi (2020) analyzed the determinants of housing prices in the Lagos residential market. This study addressed observed price discrepancies for similar housing units across and within neighbourhoods in Lagos. A descriptive analysis of the survey data collected from 751 respondents, including housing producers, intermediaries, and consumers, was conducted. The findings reveal that intermediaries significantly influence housing prices through information asymmetry. The study further concluded that intermediaries often provide incomplete or misleading information to housing consumers, resulting in prices that exceed consumers' expectations.

Oyalowo B. (2022), examined the implications of rapid urban expansion on land, planning, and housing in Lagos. Using mixed qualitative research methods, this study analyzed Lagos's significant population growth and spatial expansion within and beyond its administrative

boundaries. The study found contrasting patterns of development along different expansion axes, with formal planning mechanisms encouraging high-end real estate development, especially in coastal and planned areas, exacerbating inequalities in access to land and housing, effectively excluding lower-income families from planned developments, and undermining housing affordability. The study concluded that urban expansion in Lagos faces complex planning challenges and further demonstrated how market dynamics and planning practices contribute to unequal housing access and affordability.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study discusses the relationship between housing affordability and family stability in Lagos, Nigeria. This study adopts a descriptive cross-sectional research approach and systematically collects and analyses data from a specific location in Lagos at a specific point in time. Therefore, it is easy to identify patterns, relationships, and trends among the collected data variables without manipulating them. To facilitate data access, a physical interview with residents and printed and online questionnaires were used; hence, quantitative and qualitative elements were incorporated into the study to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

3.2 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sampling is a multistage sampling approach. Here, the Lagos state residential zones were classified into low-income areas, medium-income areas, and high-income areas based on landmarks and residents' living conditions. First-stage sampling was performed using this classification, and second-stage sampling was selected from the classified neighbourhood via systematic random sampling. A total of 50 households were sampled for this study; this sample size was considered adequate to ensure representativeness while remaining manageable within the scope and time frame of the research. The household head or an adult family member knowledgeable about housing expenses and family conditions was selected as the respondent for each household.

3.3 Measurement of Variables

To measure and assess the relationship between housing affordability and family stability and functionality, various critical parameters and indicators were considered, as listed below.

Housing affordability was measured using indicators such as the ratio of housing costs to household income, ability to meet housing payments without financial strain, and presence of housing-related debt.

Family stability was measured using indicators such as frequency of relocation, family stress and conflict levels, and children's educational continuity.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This table highlights the Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (sample space). The sample space consisted of 50 respondents, with information on age group, gender, marital status, household size, employment status, and monthly income range. A low-income salary is pegged at < 100,000, middle income at 200,000-299,999, and anything $\geq 500,000$ is considered relatively high.

S/N	Age group	Gender	Marital status	Household size	Employment status	Monthly income range
1	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
2	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
3	35-44	Male	Married	5-6	Self-employed	100,000-199,999
4	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
5	45-54	Male	Married	5-6	Formal	$\geq 500,000$
6	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
7	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Unemployed	<100,000
8	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
9	45-54	Female	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
10	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
11	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
12	45-54	Male	Married	7+	Self-employed	$\geq 500,000$
13	35-44	Female	Single	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
14	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000

15	55+	Male	Married	5-6	Self-employed	100,000-199,999
16	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
17	45-54	Male	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
19	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	≥500,000
20	45-54	Female	Married	5-6	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
21	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Unemployed	<100,000
22	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
23	45-54	Male	Married	7+	Self-employed	≥500,000
24	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Informal	100,000-199,999
25	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
26	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
27	45-54	Female	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
28	55+	Male	Married	5-6	Self-employed	≥500,000
29	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
30	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
31	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
32	45-54	Female	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
33	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
34	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	≥500,000

35	45-54	Male	Married	5-6	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
36	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
37	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
38	55+	Female	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
39	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	≥500,000
40	45-54	Female	Married	5-6	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
41	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
42	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
43	45-54	Male	Married	7+	Informal	100,000-199,999
44	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Self-employed	200,000-299,999
45	25-34	Male	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
46	55+	Male	Married	5-6	Self-employed	≥500,000
47	35-44	Female	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999
48	45-54	Male	Married	5-6	Informal	100,000-199,999
49	25-34	Female	Single	1-2	Informal	<100,000
50	35-44	Male	Married	3-4	Formal	200,000-299,999

Table 1: Filled Household Socio-Economic Data (50 Households)

The graph below shows the ratio of tenants to household owners from the 50 selected sample spaces above. This graph shows that 7% of the sample space are homeowners and 93% are tenant.

Figure 1: sample space data of household

This graph shows the relationship between annual income and annual house rent for the sample space, grouped by income level: high, medium, and low. This graph explains that from every salary earned (assuming to be 100% independent of the amount), most high-income earners spend approximately 30% of their total salary on rent, medium-income earners spend approximately 55%, and low-income earners spend 65-70% of their salaries on house rent.

Figure 2: Annual income Vs Annual house rent

This graph shows the relationship between housing burden cost and family stability; it indicates that family stability increases with a lower housing burden cost. To estimate the housing burden cost,

$$\text{Housing Cost Burden (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total Annual Housing cost}}{\text{Total Annual Household Income}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The simple average method was employed to quantify family stability. The indicators of family stability were summed and averaged depending on the total number of indicators.

$$\text{Family stability score} = \frac{a+b+c+d+e}{n} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

- *a* = Frequency of relocation in last 5 years
- *b* = Ability to meet household needs after paying rent
- *c* = Level of family conflict due to housing costs
- *d* = School continuity of children
- *e* = Perceived family cohesion
- *n* = number of indicators; in this case is 5

Figure 3: Family stability score Vs Housing burden cost

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study clearly demonstrate that housing affordability is a critical determinant of family stability in the Lagos metropolitan context. There is an inverse relationship between housing cost burden and family stability. An increase in the housing cost burden decreases the family stability score.

Households with lower housing cost burdens depict family stability, which reflects a low frequency of relocation in the last five years and sufficient funds to meet other family responsibilities comfortably after paying house rent. This also shows that children are unlikely to change schools because of relocation.

On the other hand, families with almost all of their annual income allocated to house rent experience much residential mobility, and hence, children tend to change schools more often in these families. There is a low capacity to meet the needs of the family.

Overall, the findings confirm that housing affordability is not merely a shelter issue but a fundamental concern for social stability. Persistent housing cost burdens in Lagos contribute directly to reduced family stability, reinforcing socioeconomic vulnerability and inequality across income groups.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Strengthening Rent Regulation**

The Lagos State Ministry of Lands and Housing should implement stricter measures to curb arbitrary rent increases and excessive intermediary charges by housing and real estate agents.

- **Expansion of Affordable Housing Supply**

The Lagos State Government should partner with other private real estate companies to construct affordable housing units, particularly for low-income households.

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